

HONORARIUM GUIDELINES FOR INVOLVING CITIZENS AND STAKEHOLDERS IN RESEARCH

Citizens, people affected by research (e.g., patients and their relative, practitioners, health experts) and stakeholders (e.g., NPOs/NGOs, associations, public administration, companies, health care or educational institutions) can be actively involved in research in a variety of ways. For example, they can become advisory board or steering group members and advise scientists on planned research, they identify research topics and research questions together with scientists, help shape the research design, co-design project information and materials, collect, analyze, and interpret data, or disseminate research results to the public. All activities must be directly related to and carried out with stakeholder involvement. For more information and ideas on how to involve stakeholders in research, see: [Kaisler & Missbach \(2019\)](#) and [Wellcome](#).

As a token of appreciation for their work, the OIS Center recommends that everyone involved in the research project shall be compensated with an honorarium. The persons involved in the research project are not obligated to accept honorarium payments. They can also be compensated with a non-monetary equivalent (e.g., vouchers, group excursions, language courses). The involved persons can also donate their honorarium payments. Alternative honorarium payments should be considered especially for self-employed persons, social welfare recipients or persons who do not have a bank account. To avoid misunderstandings and problems, an open and clear communication on the part of the project leaders about honorarium payments before actively involving persons in the research process is strongly recommended.

Regardless of the honorarium, travel expenses, catering costs, costs for support persons, etc. of the persons involved in the research project can be reimbursed.

The OIS Center recommends the following honorarium guidelines¹ for the different forms of involvement in research:

EUR 15.00 - EUR 20.00: For participating in a task or activity such as reading and commenting on documents that takes less than half an hour; e.g., reviewing documents for a call for proposal.

EUR 30.00 - EUR 40.00: For participating in a task or activity that requires little or no preparation and takes about an hour or less; e.g., participating in a focus group to provide feedback on a project idea.

EUR 60.00 - EUR 80.00: For participation in a task or activity that requires some preparation and takes about two hours; e.g., a conference call that requires reading or reviewing documents in advance.

¹ The guidelines are based on the [recommendations of the National Institute of Health Research](#) (UK) and current practices at the LBG OIS Center.

EUR 90.00 - EUR 120.00: For participation in a task or activity that requires some preparation and takes approximately half a day; e.g., attending a selection meeting to interview candidates for a committee or panel, participating in a focus group, or conducting a training session.

EUR 180.00 - EUR 240.00: For attending full-day meetings; e.g., attending a committee or panel meeting as an observer before becoming an active member of the committee/panel.

EUR 360.00 - EUR 480.00: For attending full-day meetings that require extensive preparation; e.g., for (co-)chairing a meeting or for other volunteer duties that require additional responsibility.

EUR 540.00 - EUR 720.00: For participation in full-day meetings that require extensive preparation and high responsibility; e.g., participation in a selection meeting to decide on funding for submitted projects.

If you have any questions, please contact:

LBG OIS Center - Team Involvement

Dr. Christiane Grill christiane.grill@lbg.ac.at

Thomas Palfinger, MSc thomas.palfinger@lbg.ac.at